

Research Science and Innovation House

CERTIFICATE

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Acumen: international journal of multidisciplinary research
of participation

The certificate is presented to

Mursalov Muhammadzohid

For publication of the research article

**THEME: HUQUQ SOHASI VA HUQUQ INSTITUTI TUSHUNCHALARI HAQIDA
TAHLIL**

**EDITOR-IN-CHIEF
Eshkaraev S.Ch**

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